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List of Abbreviations

AC	Alternating Current
ADC	Analog-to-Digital
AFE	Analog-Front-End
API	Application Programming Interface
CPU	Central Processing Unit
dB	Decibels
DC	Direct Current
DMA	Direct Memory Access
DMU	DC Measurement Unit
DREQ	Data Request
DSP	Digital Signal Processing
FSM	Finite State Machine
GPS	Global Positioning System
HAT	Hardware-Attached-on-Top
IC	Integrated Circuit
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
kHz	Kilo-Hertz
kSps	Kilo-Samples-per-Second
LTI	Linear Time Invariant
LSB	Least Significant Bit
MQTT	MQ Telemetry Transport
m	milli
n	Nano
OS	Operative System
PMU	Phasor Measurement Unit
ppm	Parts-per-Million
PPS	Pulse-per-Second
PWM	Pulse Width Modulation
RMS	Root Mean Square
ROCOF	Rate of Change of Frequency
RPi3	Raspberry Pi 3
SMI	Secondary Memory Interface
SMU	Synchronized Measurement Unit
TCP	Transfer Control Protocol
TLS	Transport Layer Security
V	Volts
WP	Work Package
μ	Micro
Ω	Ohm

Executive Summary

The Synchronized Measurement Unit (SMU), as a generalization of the Phasor Measurement Unit (PMU) for both, Alternating Current (AC) and Direct Current (DC) systems, is a single device able to provide synchronized measurements to a time-referenced signal using Global Positioning System (GPS). This concept, developed within the present project and explored within the first chapter, tries to solve different problems within the power grid, like lack of reference points for measurements and long-distance measurements that would require long cables. The SMU, in particular, uses a Raspberry Pi 3-based platform with specific-purpose hardware including a 3D-printed housing for the digitalization of physical values (current and voltages). On the other hand, its different software layers include a low-level driver for data acquisition and higher-level plugins in charge of the data processing. At the end of every main chapter, a special emphasis on the DC operation of the SMU is made, where we call the device as DC Measurement Unit (DMU) to specify the joint hardware and software configurations that characterize it for the DC operation.

In the second chapter, a special emphasis on the Hardware dimension of the DMU is given, where a detailed description of the Hardware-Attached-on-Top (HAT) board is given, where the Analog-to-Digital (ADC) and the GPS block are present, providing the RPi3 with a digital interface to the physical world and a time reference block for a deterministic time frame for the acquired variables respectively. Moreover, the ADC block is not just dependent on the ADC specifications but also on other components of the analog front end, reaching up to 200kSps, $\pm 10V$ full-range, for eight simultaneous acquisition channels with up to 16-bit precision, while the GPS block provides with sub-microsecond sample-synchronization. In between the performed tests include static as well as a dynamic error quantification (with an offset error of $46\mu V$ and gain error of 216ppm, significantly less error than 1%), transient conditions (group delay of $14.9\mu s$ to reach 50% of the full-range-scale step-signal), and synchronization error (roughly 188.7ns). Finally, a schematic circuit description for the DMU hardware connection and operation is presented.

In the third chapter, the software architecture of the SMU is explored, where it can be customized to operate as a DMU, PMU, or any other synchronous measurement device. Furthermore, the software layer consists of several blocks, including smuDRV, smuSVC, smuLIB, smuDSP, and smuNET. First, the smuDRV operates as a driver module that uses a finite state machine to acquire data and govern the operation of the HAT board. Second, the smuSVC interfaces with the driver to provide the acquired data to the userspace. The third block, smuLIB provides the different modules with common information and registries to avoid the need for copy-pasting the same data several times. Fourth, the smuDSP is in charge of processing the samples to provide different results from the digitalized analog values. Finally, the smuNET block provides network and communication, providing the data to other programs in need of processed results. Altogether, the first three can be considered as general-purpose blocks, while the last two define mainly the type and characteristics of the Operation as either DMU or PMU. In this case, libraries for raw samples and RMS, DC and AC compressed data formats have been currently prepared for DC systems within the possible smuDSP libraries to be selected, as well as MQTT and TCP server for communication protocols implemented within the smuNET libraries to support the interface of external applications.

In the fourth chapter, the recommendation for a future standard for DMU is discussed and emphasized into two main topics. Firstly, the definition of the extent of the Measurement System must be addressed, where consideration should be given to the signal level adaptation stage, signal conditioning stage, and signal acquisition and processing stage. Secondly, dif-

ferent errors involved in the measurement process should be defined, including static signal error, dynamic signal error, transient error, and synchronization error. Recommendations are provided for each of these errors, with a maximum deviation of 1% recommended for dynamic signal error, and static signal error for the RMS, DC and AC components individually, while a transient error of no more than 2% should be considered for a full-range step-response. A synchronization error of less than 10 μ s is recommended (i.e. 1% of 1kSps).

Finally, as a conclusion for this Work Package (WP) deliverable, several improvement points have been identified, separated mainly into Hardware and Software improvements. Regarding the Hardware, a surge protection stage, a signal conditioning stage, and fault-tolerant hardware additions, as well as their impact on the measurement are still to be explored within the project. For the Software improvements, the validity of the compressed data proposed within the project is to be reviewed. Further CPU compatibility, code optimization, code maintainability, as well as new communication libraries, and a fault-tolerant operation software layer represent further project needs.

1 Introduction

With the invention of the GPS, the phasor concept evolved into a wider technique, which adds an absolute time reference to the phasors calculation, thus, giving the possibility of synchronizing the measures of distant stations without any physical connections to the field instruments but the very transmission lines that join together the different parts of the system.

As the dynamics of AC power systems require the rupture of the classical phasor assumption by which the frequency is considered as static. Then, besides the magnitude and phase of the classical phasor representation, it is added the frequency (represented as a deviation of the fundamental frequency) and the ROCOF, both of them consequences of the different mathematical approach and essential to know the system's frequency deviation and trigger the proper corrective actions according to its current trend. A commercial usage example of a PMU is illustrated in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: Commercial PMU within E ON Research Center (ACS-RWTH laboratory).

SMU is a concept that emerges from PMU, also known as Synchronized Phasor Measurement Unit (Phadke, 2002), an exclusively AC linked concept that emerged during the second half of the 1990s and found increased adoption at the beginnings of the present century. SMUs, then, represent a more general concept developed within the RWTH-Aachen University for AC as well as DC, jointly developed under the project HYPERRIDE. In this particular case we explored the principles of the PMU for its adoption in novel Direct Current (DC) grid projects and research.

Moreover, SMUs are measurement units whose measurements are synchronized to a time-referenced signal, in this particular case, with GPS satellite signals which provide a sub-microsecond time reference for the acquired values. These units are intended to solve problems like the lack of measurements reference points for time-varying values (e.g. phasor-angle for

AC Power Grids or Faults tracking for DC and AC Power Grids) or long-distance measurements that might make the extension of measurement cables prohibitive, either financially or technically (e.g. the potential difference between two points in a Power Transmission line, necessary for the voltage regulation, power losses calculation, etc.).

1.1 Synchronized Measurement Application Examples

The simplifications of phasor representation provides advantages for local systems, allowing fast and easy calculations of the state of the variables for the new configuration. For complex power systems, such localized simplifications start causing problems as the measured variables are scattered along wide areas. Measurement of variables over long distances using the classical concepts influence measurement quality negatively as high delays and error deviations invalidate the results. The alternative to such localized assumptions is to record measurement data from all of these localized points using high-quality measurement cables, which in turn is unfeasible due to mismatched reference frames between such localized points. Figure 2 presents a representation of an unfeasible measurement concept in power systems:

Figure 2: Representation of an Unfeasible Measurement Concept in Power Systems.

Due to shortcomings of the classical measurement concept, synchronized measurement is proposed as a reliable alternative. As the reference is now set as a GPS-aligned sampling that allow the comparison of two or more different points, utilizing DMUs connected to these specific points, as illustrated in Figure 3:

Figure 3: Representation of a Synchronized Measurement Concept.

Within the Synchronized Measurement concept, several applications are now introduced:

- **Power Flow Analysis:** It is employed to determine the most favorable operating conditions for a power system based on the load. The calculations are performed based on the voltage and current readings at the buses where the DMUs are connected. Generally, power flow analysis is employed to calculate the steady-state operational characteristics of a power system, including but not limited to bus voltages and currents. Importantly, power flow analysis operates on a deterministic basis: all measurements are accurate and available, with no gaps in data or inaccuracies.
- **State Estimation:** It is utilised to estimate the real-time operational state of a power system by analysing measurements obtained from the system. To achieve the most accurate estimation of the state of the power system, optimization methods are employed to minimise measurement errors and estimate missing data. Unlike power flow analysis, state estimation acknowledges the potential presence of missing or erroneous data. The outcome of the state estimation process is the most reliable approximation of the true operational state of the power system, encompassing parameters such as voltages and currents at each bus.
- **Line Parameter Estimation:** Line parameter estimation in power systems involves the identification of the electrical characteristics of power lines. These characteristics encompass crucial parameters such as resistance, inductance, capacitance, and conductance, which play a vital role in the modelling and analysis of power system behavior. Accurate estimation enables precise power flow analysis and necessitates regular monitoring to accommodate changes in line characteristics, thereby ensuring reliable and efficient power system operation.

In the bullet points above, potential applications using DMUs based on an example synchronised measurement configuration shown in Figure 3, where the minimum number of required variables for each specific measurement application are also provided.

1.2 The Synchronized Measurement Unit Development

The Synchronized Measurement Unit (SMU) used in this project is a Raspberry Pi 3 (RPI3) (Ltd, n.d.) based platform used for collecting data that consists of multiple software and hardware layers (see Figure 4). The hardware includes a HAT with a 3D-printed housing. On the other hand, the software layer includes the driver that operates at a low level, and the daemon as well as the plugins that operate at a higher level.

Figure 4: SMU layers: hardware (blue, left) and software (right, gray, and red).

For improved clarity or a deeper technical understanding of the presented architecture, we recommend consulting (Guarnieri Calò Carducci, Pau, et al., 2022). The present report shows the SMU through its different layers and sub-layers in separate sections, emphasizing the DC operation as synchronized DC Measurement Unit (DMU), to be called in this way to differentiate it from the “General Purpose” SMU.

Finally, the open-source hardware and software repository of the SMU developed within the framework of the present project can be found in (Guarnieri Calò Carducci, Casal, & Sowa, 2022)¹.

¹<https://git.rwth-aachen.de/acs/public/automation/smu>

2 Hardware

As the hardware layer of the SMU consists again of two sub-layers (i.e., electronic and mechanical; see Figure 5), we will dive into the electronic characteristics, as the mechanical layer depends on the application and presentation of the device. Said this, the main blocks present within the electronic sub-layer (both integrated within the HAT board) are classified as:

- The analog-to-digital converter block: providing a digital interface to the physical world.
- The time reference block: to ensure a deterministic time frame for the acquired variables.

Figure 5: View of the SMU within a DIN-Rail mountable enclosure.

The HAT board (Figure 6) as previously introduced, connects directly to the 40-pin header of a RPi3 (see Figure 7 and Figure 8), complementing in this way the elements needed to provide a Linear Time Invariant (LTI) Digital acquisition system for further data processing of the Analog-Acquired signals. More in detail, the Analog-Front-End (AFE) of the board is based on the Texas Instruments ADS8588S (*ADS8588S data sheet, product information and support | TI.com, n.d.*) or ADS8578S (*ADS8578S data sheet, product information and support | TI.com, n.d.*) Integrated Circuit (IC), which is either 16-bit or 14-bit (respectively), 8-channel ADC module that can achieve sample rates up to 200kSps.

The device supports multiple digital interfaces, but the SMU design uses parallel byte mode to achieve the maximum sample rate using only 8 digital data pins. Optionally, the board can be configured with external differential low-pass filters to reduce ADC bandwidth or match the impedance with a specific sensor. For its use as DMU, the optional filter can be either completely removed or tuned to a high cut-off frequency in order to avoid the integration of the measured voltage.

The Secondary Memory Interface (SMI) of the RPi3 automatically handles the transfer of data from the ADC, which is explained later in more detail. It is important to add that the ADC sampling base is generated by the Central Processing Unit (CPU) using the internal Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) of the RPi3, associated with the audio channel of the RPi3.

The SMU uses a u-blox MAX M8C (*MAX-M8 series, 2015*) GPS module to achieve precise synchronization, with which it obtains the Pulse-per-Second (PPS) signal. Then, the SMU uses

Figure 6: SMU hardware-attached-on-top module for Raspberry Pi 3 and main board components.

Figure 7: Side view of the SMU, with inputs and peripherals.

the PPS to generate a train of pulses at periodic intervals for the sampling base needed for the ADC. This creates a one-shot synchronization mechanism that resets any jitter that may have accumulated during the previous period, ensuring the required LTI behavior for further digital signal processing.

On the other hand, user-space programs cannot perform interrupt-signal detection within the raspberry pi, relying on a poorly synchronized polling request, addressed by the Operative System (OS). However, the SMI interface provides a solution for this by programming a Data Request (DREQ) pin to pace the data transfer. When combined with Direct Memory Access (DMA), can achieve synchronous sampling with less than a microsecond of error. However,

Figure 8: View of the SMU HAT mounted on top of a Raspberry Pi. It can be seen compared to a 2€ coin (on the left).

since the SMI data request interrupt is level-sensitive, the design includes two monostable multivibrators with Schmitt trigger inputs to achieve the appropriate duration and edge required by the raspberry pi's processor. An OR gate is then used to merge the triggers into one signal to control the DMA.

2.1 Error Quantification

Tests and measurements were conducted in (Guarnieri Calò Carducci, Pau, et al., 2022) to analyze the performance of the SMU under different conditions, including static, dynamic, and transient conditions. The performance of the SMU is not just dependent on the ADC specifications, but also on other components of the analog front end and the overall system. The tests mentioned in the present section correspond to the NI USB 6356, a National Instruments DAQ device with a signal accuracy of 331ppm over the mentioned $\pm 10V$ scale.

2.1.1 Static Error

The static characterisation of the SMU involves measuring the data provided by the ADC while applying a linear voltage ramp to the input across the entire full-scale range (i.e. from $-10V$ to $+10V$). The error is quantified as $-45.3\mu V$ and the gain error as 216ppm. The uncertainty linked to this estimation can be evaluated from the covariance matrix of the residuals, but it was found to be much smaller ($168\mu V$) than the manufacturing tolerance. Systematic errors of the static

characteristic and the linear regression residuals are represented in Figure 9 and Figure 10 respectively:

Figure 9: SMU's Static Systematic (Source: (Guarnieri Calò Carducci, Pau, et al., 2022)).

Figure 10: Linear Regression Residuals calculated for the SMU (Source: (Guarnieri Calò Carducci, Pau, et al., 2022)).

2.1.2 Dynamic Error

Dynamic Error aims to determine the frequency response of the measurement device while considering the impact of system noise and non-ideal sampling clock. In this case the lowpass filter with cutoff frequency is 99kHz. The results show a bandwidth of 21.2kHz (3dB) and a constant gain of -0.1dB over 5.6kHz, which is due to the addition of an external low-pass input filter before the ADC. Below, in Figure 11, frequency response of amplitude and phase values are presented:

Figure 11: Frequency Response of the SMU (Source: (Guarnieri Calò Carducci, Pau, et al., 2022)).

2.1.3 Transient Error

The transient test is used to determine the group delay and synchronization delay of the SMU. The Group delay is measured by observing the step response when the input is varied instantly, and the results show that the SMU has a group delay of 14.9 μ s to reach 50% of the set point value, an overshoot of 13.4%, with a settling time of 63 μ s. The value of group delay obtained from the test is similar to the typical value declared by the manufacturer. Figure 12 illustrates the transient response of the SMU.

2.1.4 Synchronisation Error

The difference between the measured value and the declared value in terms of time error (or time delay) is due to the synchronization error, which was found to be 188.7 ± 2.7 ns in 92.4% of the cases (almost 3-sigma). As seen below, Figure 13 highlights the synchronisation error of the SMU.

Figure 12: Transient Response of the SMU (Source: (Guarnieri Calò Carducci, Pau, et al., 2022)).

Figure 13: Quantile Plot for the SMU's Synchronisation Delay Quantile (Source: (Guarnieri Calò Carducci, Pau, et al., 2022)).

2.2 Physical Connection for DMU operation

As presented in Figure 4, the input signal for voltage as well as current should be adapted in order to operate within the range from -5V to +5V ($\pm 5V$) or from -10V to +10V ($\pm 10V$), as the ADS85X8 (*ADS8588S data sheet, product information and support | TI.com, n.d.*) (*ADS8578S data sheet, product information and support | TI.com, n.d.*) within the HAT board is intended to operate in any of these ranges.

Originally, the default operational range is $\pm 10V$, while, for an operation within the smaller amplitude window a modification to a variable within the smuDRV library is necessary. As shown in Figure 14, a signal transformation is necessary in order to fall within the correct range of voltage, in this case in the form of a resistive divider for the case of Voltage sensing, or a Hall sensor able to provide a signal within the predefined range is recommended.

An important remark is a need for protection against voltage transients with fast action (considering the electronic nature of the SMU) for any voltage superior to $\pm 10V$, with a maximum rating of $\pm 15V$ referenced to the analog-input grounding. Considering these, surge arrestors for fast electromagnetic pulses or varistors are recommended for analog-inputs protection.

Figure 14: Connection Diagram of the SMU for DMU operation.

3 Software

The software layer of the SMU consists of several blocks as shown in Figure 15:

- The smuDRV: a driver for low-level interaction between the HAT board and the RPi3 processor.
- The smuSVC: which is a data acquisition program in charge of providing the acquired data to the userspace.
- The smuLIB: A library shared by the different submodules with common information for the different submodules.
- The smuDSP: A user-defined library in charge of processing the samples in order to provide different results from the digitalized analog values.
- The smuNET: for network and communication, is in charge of providing the data to other programs in the need for the processed results provided by the smuDSP.

Figure 15: Software architecture with the user-configurable submodules in red.

As the smuDRV, as well as the smuSVC present a less-configurable interface for a technical user (who is not the end-user of the programmed SMU) as well as this module, does not define the final application of the SMU, we will provide a general description of these programs altogether.

3.1 smuDRV & smuSVC

The smuDRV mechanism operates in the Kernel-Space as a driver module and resembles a Finite State Machine (FSM), which makes it highly reliable and autonomous despite the Operative's systems stochastic nature. The kernel driver operates independently of the CPU load, and the data acquisition FSM leaves the CPU completely unused, allowing the four cores to be fully dedicated to data processing and auxiliary functions, acquiring the timing and providing an ADC time-base for sampling to later pass the results to the User-Space program awaiting for the acquired data: the smuSVC.

After the data is acquired and transferred to the user space, it can be processed and analyzed. The SMU provides an Application Programming Interface (API) for the dynamic binding of external libraries, which can be developed using the smuDSP and smuNET plug-ins. These libraries can implement a wide range of data processing and networking functionalities, enabling the SMU to be finally customized to operate as DMU, PMU, or any other different synchronous measurement device.

The samples acquired from the ADC are transferred in fixed-size blocks, which can be configured through a configuration file. Once the transfer is complete, the smuDRV notifies the smuSVC (also known as “daemon”), which can then read the data from the buffer and process it. To end the data acquisition process, the daemon sends a signal to the driver to stop the transfer. This stops the DMA transfer and disables the conversion base. Subsequently, the driver notifies the daemon that the acquisition has been terminated.

The driver informs the daemon about the position in the buffer where the latest was written, using a signal with a memory position index as an argument, that should be read by the Digital Signal Processing (DSP) services defined by the user. The driver provides samples equivalent to 10ms of data acquisition, corresponding to a maximum buffer frame (i.e. a group or “batch” of samples) rate of 100 frames per second, which can be reduced if needed.

3.2 smuDSP & smuNET

The processing and network libraries used in the system are dynamic libraries linked to the daemon memory map during runtime. These libraries have three functions:

- init: for memory allocation and initialization/configuration steps
- exit: for memory deallocation and exit steps
- proc: for data processing, formatting, and logging

This design allows the easy replacement of processing libraries and the potential support of multiple new libraries in the future. The separation between the core service and the plugins also enables the development of libraries with different licensing schemes that can integrate with the platform.

Once a buffer frame is filled with acquired data, the driver sends a "data_ready" signal, which is received by the daemon. The daemon forwards this signal to the corresponding smuDSP library along with the memory position with new data. The user-defined library processes the data, applies a timestamp, and fills the result buffer with proper information. When the timestamp matches an integer multiple of the reporting period, the smuDSP plugin sends a second "data_ready" signal to the smuNET plugin. The smuNET plugin prepares the data according to the desired data protocol and sends it to a defined network host. In this way, the data is processed and transmitted to the network host seamlessly.

3.3 smuDSP for DMU Operation

While the phasor representation of AC signals includes amplitude, angular frequency, and initial phase, in the case of pure DC current, the fundamental frequency is zero. In power systems, pulsating DC current often includes various AC components with different frequencies superimposed on the DC component. Therefore, three different components need to be extracted from raw samples when dealing with DC power systems.

- Root Mean Square (RMS): Defined physically as the value equivalent to a DC signal that would produce the same power dissipation in a resistive load (see “Root-mean-square value” in (Daintith, 2009)). This information comprises both, AC and DC components altogether.

$$x_{\text{RMS}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} x_i^2} \quad (1)$$

$$x_{\text{RMS(AC+DC)}} = \sqrt{x_{\text{DC}}^2 + x_{\text{AC(RMS)}}^2} \quad (2)$$

- Average value: Average Value, which can provide an estimation of the pure DC component. This is because periodic signals and white noise have an average of zero. It is important to choose an appropriate time-window period to avoid the influence of lower frequency harmonic components on the error. This average can be obtained as:

$$x_{\text{AVG}} = x_{\text{DC}} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} x_i \quad (3)$$

- AC component: By subtracting the RMS and average values from the raw signal samples, we can obtain the AC component of the signal. This provides us with information about the pulsating components in the power system, which can affect the final results in terms of power and energy.

$$x_{\text{RMS(AC)}} = \sqrt{x_{\text{RMS}}^2 + x_{\text{AVG}}^2} \quad (4)$$

Finally, it is important to add that the errors associated to the three components, as it can be appreciated from all the formulas presented in this subsection, strictly depend on the sampling frequency adopted by the ADC. For this case, the ADC sampling frequency is linearly related to the computational complexity, in consequence, an increase in the mentioned frequency presents a linear growth in the complexity as well, up to a point where the processor’s limitation leads to a rupture in the provision of the samples, for these circumstances we recommend either a reduction in the number of samples-per-second or a reduction in the computational complexity of the problem by the reduction of operations involved in the result provision.

3.3.1 smuNET for DMU Operation

In this case, due to the lack of standards for Synchronized Values provision in DC networks, the DMU networking library has been developed in order to fulfill commonly used protocols in smart energy applications. Under these circumstances, the DMU provides the following data upon the previous configuration:

- MQ Telemetry Transport (MQTT) messages report of Raw Samples: With a sampling rate of 10kSps (10 kilo-samples per second) per every channel, with 10 sample-frames per second (i.e. 1000 samples-per-frame, per-channel). A Timestamp defines the frame start, so, the exact position of every specific sample should be calculated from the reference timestamp provided in order to reconstruct the signal.
- MQTT message report of RMS, DC, and AC components of the signal with a report of 10 frames per second. A Timestamp defines the middle point of the frame.

- Transfer Control Protocol (TCP) server to report RMS, DC, and AC components of the signal with a reporting rate of 10 frames per second. A Timestamp defines the middle point of the frame.

The selection of MQTT over TCP is recommended, due to the presence of Transport Layer Security (TLS), a security layer for the connection.

The package for the data provision using the mentioned protocols recommended is JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format, grouping the measurements together with channel name as well as the type of magnitude (i.e. voltage or current) being measured. The object containing the different measurements can be classified with an ID identifier (e.g. DMU1, DMU_hyperride1, etc.).

The consideration for RMS, AC, and DC components (see Figure 8) as compressed information for the signals come in hand, as the AC component might still play an important role in DC transmission as well as DC energy transformation and distribution, especially when we compare the AC and DC dissipation for diverse purposes and applications.

Figure 16: RMS value, AC, and DC components.

3.4 DMU offset and gain coefficient values

The DMU requires a set of configuration parameters in order to specify its operational behavior, for the commissioning phase.

The parameters files, named as "smuSVC.conf", besides the declaration of the algorithms and operation modes, allows also the device calibration in terms of offset values and gain factors for every individual input. The application of these factors depends directly on the program envisaged for DSP of the raw ADC data, but it is strongly recommended to apply the offset and gain coefficient values directly to the result of the DSP.

As per default, the gain coefficient values are set to 0.000305185 (i.e. $1/(2^{15} - 1)$), or $1/32767$, the maximum ADC value, considering the ADC report is a 16-bit signed integer, where 1 bit corresponds to the sign). On the other hand, the default offset is 0 (zero).

These values are to be applied as follows:

$$Val_{Final} = Val_{ADC} * Gain + Offset \quad (5)$$

3.5 Measurements Taken Using Raw Data and RMS, DC, and AC Component Libraries

Analogously to the connection diagram of Figure 14, we replaced the resistive divider and the hall sensor (both of them providing an adapted voltage signal to the DMU), by a high accuracy power supply for reference. The reference voltage was provided by a Keysight Technologies Triple Output DC Power Supply, Model E36313A with a voltage accuracy of $\pm 0.03\% + 5\text{mV}$ (i.e. \pm output error % + offset), see (Keysight, n.d.).

Moreover, the same signal was provided to two different DMUs, one running raw data reporting through MQTT and the other processing the samples in the form of RMS, DC, and AC components using the algorithms provided in Section 3.3, all of them reported through TCP. Both DMUs were connected to the same reference signal in parallel. The measurements of both devices are to be discussed in the following subsections.

During this test, the reference DC voltage signal was applied in step increments of 1V, starting from -9V, and reaching a maximum of 9V. As it can be observed in Figure 17, the DC component measured is nearly identical to the raw data measured by the second DMU.

Figure 17: Actual Measurement of DC Component and Raw Data.

Similarly, in Figure 18, the RMS voltage measured during the test can be appreciated.

Figure 18: Actual Measurement of RMS Component.

As illustrated in Figure 19, the maximum DMU relative error for raw measurements occurs around the 0V marker, as expected, with a value of 0.09145 % which is an acceptable error margin, far below 1 % as suggested in the recommendation section.

Figure 19: DMU Relative Error for Raw Measurements.

Similar to Figure 19, the DMU relative error for DC component measurement peaks around the 0V marker as well, as shown in Figure 20.

Figure 20: DMU Relative Error for DC Component Measurement.

Finally, as it can be seen in Figure 21, the DMU relative error for the RMS component measurements peak around the 0V marker, as no offset value nor gain factor correction was applied to the DMU. As it can be further inferred, the DMU relative error graph for the RMS component and the DC component are almost identical, considering a percentage error of up to 4 decimals after the point.

Figure 21: DMU Relative Error for RMS Component Measurement.

4 Recommendation for Future Standard

As no standard for synchronized DC measurement units exists yet, different considerations should be made in the process to define the different instrument errors involved. The first point to be addressed would be the definition of the extent of the DMU, where the second main topic to address should be the different errors involved in the measurement process.

4.1 Definition of the Extent of the DMU

A problem not addressed in the PMU standard (IEEE/IEC 60255-118-1-2018, see (“IEEE/IEC International Standard - Measuring relays and protection equipment - Part 118-1: Synchrophasor for power systems - Measurements”, 2018)) is the correct definition of the extent of the PMU. When it carefully addresses the different characteristics and types of errors associated with the measurement, it seems to ignore that some measurement systems might be composed of three elements, as shown in Figure 22:

- **Signal Level Adaptation Stage:** This measurement stage is in charge of providing a lower-level signal proportional to the measured variable.
- **Signal Conditioning Stage:** This measurement stage is in charge of preparing the measured value for its digitalization. In the conditioning stage we might change the variables (e.g. from current to voltage, or from certain voltage properties to other ones) as well as might provide some overvoltage as well as overcurrent protection that can impact the final measured value.
- **Signal Acquisition and Processing Stage:** This measurement stage is in charge of the Analog-to-Digital Conversion as well as the data processing of the signal. The different acquisition methods and processing algorithms can have an impact on the final result.

Figure 22: Measurement System Stages.

Commonly the Signal Level adaptation (commonly “voltage and current transformers” for the case of AC) ,as well as the Acquisition and Processing stages, are properly addressed by the different standards, the signal conditioning stages are left aside, while these might be present and exert a significant impact on the final result, possibly bigger than any of the other two

stages. In this project, for the signal conditioning stage, we have applied certain protections without a major impact, but we recommend either integrating this stage to be considered as part of the Signal Acquisition and Processing Stage or individually addressing this error source in a different section or standard.

4.2 Definitions of Errors

This subsection, based on (“IEEE/IEC International Standard - Measuring relays and protection equipment - Part 118-1: Synchrophasor for power systems - Measurements”, 2018), considers the errors that should be addressed for the standardization process, as every one of them speaks about the different signal components as well as the synchronization factor. Overall, based on the standard for PMU, we recommend paying special attention to the following factors:

- **Static Signal Error:** The error for a non-changing signal containing specified AC and DC components. The cut-off frequency for low-pass filters should consider the influence of the inverters. The recommendation is to consider together the Data Acquisition, Processing, and Signal Conditioning, altogether with a static signal error below 1% for the RMS, AC, and DC components individually.
- **Dynamic Signal Error:** This error is represented by the frequency response in terms of magnitude and phase. Here are the phase deviation as well as magnitude nonlinearities for the different frequencies. This error depends on the different frequencies that are to be considered, taking into account their influence on the grid. For the dynamic error quantification, a maximum deviation of 1% would be recommended for the intended frequencies in terms of magnitude (while phase deviation might be deprecated), including also the base converter frequency and its different harmonics, and not only the DC base frequency as the AC impact on the line should not be disregarded (e.g. due to skin effect on conductors). Considering the rapid dynamics of DC systems, this error should be able to provide correct RMS, AC, and DC information even for transients with periods above 1ms as part of the delivered information, with less than 2% of overall RMS, DC, and AC error.
- **Transient Error:** This error is introduced by the signal deformation given a signal input change with a ramp or step characteristics (this depends on the standard, but most commonly the case for unit-step is applied). Considering the rapid dynamics of DC systems, this error should be able to provide correct RMS, AC, and DC information even for transients with periods above 1ms as part of the delivered information, with less than 2% of overall RMS, DC, and AC error within the reported frame (not to be confused with the reported sample).
- **Synchronization error:** This error is associated with the digitalization and sampling signal, where the periodicity of the acquisition signal should not deviate beyond 10 microseconds from the expected period (i.e. 1% of timing error for a sampling base of 1kHz). This can be adjusted by the use of a PPS signal generated by a GPS module, with errors commonly below 1 microsecond.

5 Conclusions

The exploration of DC powered electric networks as a green and efficient alternative for the future power grid brings up some of the old problems associated with AC power networks, as it is the case for the correct measurement of voltage over long power transmission and distribution lines, setting reference points for state-estimation, power-flow calculations, or synchronous data acquisition for oscillographic studies of the network behavior. All of the mentioned problems are easily solved in AC by the employment of Synchronous PMUs, a concept that does not exist in DC due to the need for redefinition of useful data characteristics for DC Power Systems.

For this, the SMU, as a generalization of the PMU able to cover AC systems, have been proposed as part of the present project. The SMU uses a Raspberry Pi 3 for the data processing while compensating for the lack of synchronous time-source and ADC by the adoption of a HAT board developed in the framework of this project, with different software blocks that interface the HAT board with userspace data-processing and communication modules that define the operational behavior of the SMU as a specific-purpose Synchronized DMU.

More in detail, the HAT board developed for the SMU (and presented as open-source hardware) has an ADC block making use of the Texas Instruments ADS85x8s integrated circuit, able to acquire simultaneously 8-channels with a sampling frequency up to 200kSps, with up to 16-bit precision (i.e. more than 65.536 full-range divisions) within a range of $\pm 10V$. At the same time, the HAT board presents a GPS block in charge of providing sub-microsecond precision PPS, all this with static, dynamic, and synchronization errors significantly below 1%.

On the other hand, the SMU software architecture is the one that defines the customization of the device to operate as a DMU, PMU, or any synchronous measurement device. Furthermore, the software layer consists of several blocks, where the most important ones, the smuDSP, and smuNET, define the data processing method for the digitalized values, and the communication protocol to provide the required information to the application awaiting the DMU data. Currently, the DMU data provision is defined in the form of raw data, as well as RMS, DC, and AC components of the signal as DC substitutes for AC phasors.

At this point, when the specific functions of the DMU, and possible types of synchronized compressed data have been described, recommendations for a future standard for DMU have been discussed in two main topics. First, the definition of the extent of the Measurement System must be addressed, where consideration should be given to the signal level adaptation stage, signal conditioning stage, and signal acquisition and processing stage, as the middle point is currently unclear for the IEEE/IEC 60255-118-1-2018 PMU standard. Second, the different errors involved in the measurement process should be defined, including static signal error, dynamic signal error, transient error, and synchronization error, based on the mentioned AC counterpart.

Finally, several improvement points for the DMU concept have been identified, separated mainly into Hardware and Software improvements. Regarding the Hardware, a protection stage, a signal conditioning stage (as previously mentioned), and reliability additions are to be explored within the current project. For the Software improvements, the validation of the compressed data proposed as DC reading for synchronized equivalents is still required. Furthermore, CPU compatibility, code optimization, code maintainability, and new communication libraries, represent further project needs.

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Appendix A: SMU Behavior

A.1 Maximal Values Achievable at SMU Input Channels

Table 1 gives a summary of maximal values achievable at SMU input channels.

Table 1: Absolute Input Maximum Ratings for SMU Input Channels.

PARAMETER	MIN	MAX	UNIT
Analog input voltage to GND	-15	15	V
ESD overvoltage input clamp		7	kV
Connector voltage (IEC)		250	V
Connector current (IEC)		2	A

A.2 SMU's Parameters Behavior

Table 2 shows details of the different parameters defining the SMU's behavior.

Table 2: Absolute Input Maximum Ratings of SMU's Parameters Behaviour.

PARAMETER		MIN	TYP	MAX	UNIT
ANALOG INPUT					
AIN+	Positive Input	-5		5	V
		-10		10	V
AIN-	Negative Input	-5		5	V
R _{IN}	Input Impedance	0.85	1	1.15	MΩ
I _{LKG}	Input leakage current			8	μA
SYSTEM PERFORMANCE					
	Resolution (NMC)	16			bits
DNL	Differential Nonlinearity	-0.5	±0.35	0.5	LSB
INL	Integral Nonlinearity	-1.5	±0.45	1.5	LSB
E _G	Gain Error	-64	±4	64	LSB
E _{Gch}	Gain error inter-channel matching		10	60	LSB
E _O	Offset Error	-1.8	±0.15	1.8	mV
E _{Och}	Offset error inter-channel matching		0.3	2.4	mV
SAMPLING DYNAMICS					
t _{ACO}	Acquisition time	1			μs
f _s	Max throughput rate per channel	1	10	20	kSps
f _δ	Sampling frequency deviation	-19.9	-15.8	-12.5	ppm

DYNAMIC CHARACTERISTICS					
SNR	Signal-to-noise ratio		83.93		dB
THD	Total harmonic distortion (at 1 kHz)		-85.83		dB
SINAD	Signal-to-noise and distortion ratio		85.04		dB
A _{BW}	In-bandwidth signal attenuation	-0.024	-0.020	-0.017	dB
BW _{-3dB}	Small signal bandwidth	10.7	11.3	11.9	kHz
SYNCHRONIZATION DYNAMICS					
t _{REF}	Time reference accuracy		10		ns
t _{DEL}	Time synchronization delay	4.5	6.3	14.6	μs
PHASOR DYNAMICS					
TVE	Total Vector Error		0.82	1.24	%
FE	Frequency Error		0.1		mHz

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